

Resurrection

Levels of Difficulty
[Super Extended 2 (ChatGPT Version)]

Abstract: I've outlined various hypothetical levels of difficulty for achieving resurrection based on scientific principles, each level targeting different aspects and scopes of resurrection. These levels range from utilizing the DNA of a specific individual for reconstruction to recreating all living beings in the observable universe since the Big Bang.

Here's a summary of each level:

Level 1: Within 3 centuries, targeting the DNA of a specific individual, with a difficulty level of Medium. Personnel involved are humans, and the territory located after resurrection is Planet Earth.

Level 2: Within 4-5 centuries, targeting the DNA of successors (descendants), with an advanced difficulty level. Personnel involved are humans, and the territory located after resurrection is Planet Earth.

Level 3: Within 1 millennium, targeting random particles in the universe, with a very advanced difficulty level. Personnel involved include humans and partially aliens. Territory located after resurrection is Planet Earth.

Level 4: Within 1 million years, targeting random particles in the universe, with unspecified difficulty level. Personnel involved are humans and mostly aliens. This level aims to recreate approximately 100-106 billion people, and the territory located after resurrection is the Solar System.

Level 5: Within 3.2 million years, targeting random particles in the universe. Only aliens are involved, with unspecified difficulty level. This level aims to recreate approximately 100-106 billion people, plus an unspecified number of non-human creatures. Territory located after resurrection is the Milky Way galaxy.

Level 6: Within 1 billion years, targeting random particles in the universe. Only aliens are involved, with unspecified difficulty level. This level aims to recreate all living creatures in the observable universe since the Big Bang, including an unspecified number of non-human and non-terrestrial creatures. Territory located after resurrection is the Observable Universe.

Conclusion: Each level represents an increasingly complex and expansive scope of resurrection, with the last level encompassing the entirety of the observable universe.

Note: This manuscript was written with the help of ChatGPT.

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Albi Ndoni
Tirana, Albania
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